
THE ROLE OF COLLEGES AND INFLIBNET CENTER TO ACCESS E-RESOURCES OF NLIST PROGRAMME

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Abstract:

The present study tries to find out the status of colleges registered with NLIST programme. The recent data was collected from various websites. In India there are 36 states including 8 union territories. In the analysis of data, it is found that, there are 42343 colleges in various states of India. Out of which only 14.58 % colleges are registered for NLIST programme in September 2022. Further analysis shows that, out of registered colleges 64.75% (3999) had renewed the membership of NLIST for year 2022-23 and the number is increasing gradually. The study shows that majority of colleges have not registered. The INFLIBNET center plays major role in connecting colleges with NLIST E-resources and needs to do more to increase the number of registration. The ratio of active users to beneficiary colleges is 154.12. The data of all states with registration and renewal statistics is presented in the data analysis section of the paper. State of Maharashtra and Karnataka have majority of colleges registered and active. There is no college in Daman & Diu registered with NLIST. The administrators of all colleges must take steps to register and renew NLIST membership regularly. The study also suggests that awareness and training programs should be increased to reach more users. It will help students, researchers and faculty members to improve the quality of education, research and overall growth of the nation.

Keywords: NLIST, INFLIBNET, College Library, Higher Education, E-Resources.

Introduction:

In developing countries like India; Higher Education Institutes (HEIs) are facing economic difficulties. It leads to shortening the required supply of all types of resources to the academic community. As compared to Books and Journals in print form, electronic format has become more convenient because of the availability of various handy technologies in the society. To overcome the lack of funds; Governments also giving support to these institutes by providing E-Resources

in the form of consortia, which fulfills the need up to some extent. In this digital era the university and college libraries are converted themselves into Hybrid Libraries. Nowadays libraries are focused on using E-Resources rather than printed resources and the covid pandemic busted it up. NAAC also promotes HEIs to use E-Resources so that they can reach all stakeholders easily. Initially UGC created different consortia for different HEIs. Due to the need of the time they all are combined in NLIST consortia. Library

consortium is a collective activity of a group of libraries to cope up with the economic difficulties.(Joydip Chandra, 2011)

The project NLIST (National Library and Information Services Infrastructure for Scholarly Content) is jointly executed by the e-ShodhSindhu Consortium, INFLIBNET Centre and the INDEST-AICTE Consortium. The project provides access to students, researchers and faculty from colleges and other beneficiaries through server(s) installed at the INFLIBNET. The registered users can access and download articles required by them directly from the publisher's website once they are registered authorized users through servers deployed at the INFLIBNET Centre. In Year 2014, N-LIST programme is added under e-ShodhSindhu Consortium as college component.

After reviewing the literature available on NLIST and other e-resources, this study was initiated to know the status of the colleges in India, having registered for NLIST and being active by renewing the membership. The active membership is the only way for users to get access to the e-resources available through NLIST consortium.

Literature Review:

Current status of Higher Education Institutes in India:

As per 'All India Survey on Higher Education 2019-20', there are 1043 Universities, 42343 Colleges and 11779 Stand Alone Institutions listed on AISHE web portal. Out of them 6176 (14.58%) colleges have registered for NLIST membership, among them 3999 colleges are active beneficiary colleges.

Features of E-Resources:

The main pros of E-Resources in the libraries are: a) Easy access to information any where any time to any one without physical existence. b) It is easy to display materials that are in inaccessible formats, like large volumes or maps. c) Comparatively economical and easy for integration into teaching materials. d) Access to related material through linkage. e) Enhanced search ability, including full text. f) Integration of different media (images, sounds, video, etc.) g) The ability to satisfy requests for surrogates (photocopies, photographic prints, slides, etc.).(Karmakar et al., 2012)

Our great Tamil poet Bharathi insists that go around the eight directions to bring the knowledge to our nation, now we can get the required knowledge and information within the room and need not go outside to get it. In the modern information era many types of e-resources are available. Academicians are using e-resources for their teaching as well as research work. E-books, E-journals, databases are becoming more popular and widely used because of their special features. E-resources are published before print resources because latest information must reach to end user very quick and fast. In this era, to meet the fast growth of information demands of the college library users and overcoming the problem of resource crunch, the project N-LIST was formed by INFLIBNET Centre. The N-LIST consortia project provides access to E-resources to students, researchers and faculty from colleges and other beneficiary institutions through servers installed at the INFLIBNET Centre, India.(Annadurai & Venkatachalam, 2015)

Consortia Concept:

The 'Consortia' word was originated from Latin in early 19th century in the sense of partnership. The term 'consortia' is derived from the field of 'Economics' and refers to the grouping together of different independent companies in order to bring together financial or material resources under a single managing body for the collective performance of specific operations. According to encyclopedic dictionary of library and information science that an association of independent libraries and for library systems established by formal agreement, usually for the purpose of resource sharing. Membership may be restricted to a specific geographic region, type of library or subject specialization. Oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary describes Consortia as 'a group of people, countries, companies, etc who are working together on a particular project'. A library Consortia is an association of a group of libraries that agree to share their resources to satisfy the needs of users. Consortia may be formed on a local, regional, national, or international basis; on a functional or format basis; or on a subject basis. A consortium could be described as a group of organizations who come together to fulfill a combine objective that usefully requires cooperation and sharing of resources and deliver more than the sum of individual parts.(Talmale & Humbre, 2012)

Advantages of consortia - Some of the important advantages of the library consortium are as follows: (Saini, 2017)

- Available 24&7 days.
- Search bibliography / full text of article.
- Journal is available much earlier than print.

- Avoids duplication of resources.
- Provides access to wide range of e-resources at lower cost.
- Helps develop common resources database.
- Optimum utilization of funds.
- Facilities to build up digital libraries.

Disadvantages of Consortia - Some of the important disadvantages of the library consortium are as follows: (Saini, 2017)

- Copyright problems and misuse of research material.
- Absence of printed copies of journals.
- Internet access is necessary.
- Combination of essential and non-essential journals.
- Requires high initial investment in license and information and communication technology.

Need for Library Consortium:

Consortia are the collective efforts by the group of libraries to give improved services to its users through resource sharing with the help of information technology. Its need arises in view of the following scenario:

- Information explosion
- Emergence of new forms of information
- Technological developments favoring sharing of resources efficiently
- Rise in cost of resources especially journals and databases
- Inadequate library budget
- Self-sufficiency is only a dream!
- Optimum usage of resources through extended access
- Greater bargaining power with the publishers
- To bare pressure of updating the fast developing technology
- Diversity of user needs
- Survival of the library against the access to information on the www and internet.(Fernandes & Bhide, 2016)

College Library:

In general, a college library is regarded as an institution of higher learning, which usually offers three years or a four years course after school leading to a bachelor's degree. A college library must fulfill the following basic needs to support the teaching, research and study requirements of the academic community, if it is to be a place of intellectual workshop: a clear statement, which governs the relationship of the librarian and the other components of the college, like the faculty community and provides appropriately shared responsibility and activity among them; recognition of library as an academic development of the college-imparting library centered education to students as well as an academic information center with academic activities including library-based teaching.(Sen, n.d.)

Objectives:

1. To know the status of active member colleges having NLIST membership in India.

2. To highlight present status of colleges in relation with NLIST membership.
3. To find out the solution to the problems.

Scope and Limitations:

In present study, the colleges in India are covered. The study is based on the data available on NLIST and other websites in September 2022.

Methodology:

The data used for analysis was collected from NLIST and websites. It is used to study relation between the registered and nonregistered members of NLIST. The results were drawn on the basis of information collected from the websites.

Data Analysis:

The data collected from the websites was analyzed and interpreted accordingly. The state wise list of colleges registered in NLIST is given below -

Name of State	Registered	Beneficiary	Percentage
Andaman & Nicobar Islands	2	2	100.00
Andhra Pradesh	258	175	67.83
Arunachal Pradesh	8	5	62.50
Assam	248	195	78.63
Bihar	146	38	26.03
Chandigarh	1	0	0.00
Chhattisgarh	188	138	73.40
Dadara and Nagar Haveli	2	2	100.00
Delhi	76	66	86.84
Goa	33	31	93.94
Gujarat	430	98	22.79
Haryana	166	120	72.29
Himachal Pradesh	52	34	65.38
Jammu and Kashmir	100	71	71.00

Jharkhand	104	63	60.58
Karnataka	734	486	66.21
Kerala	288	241	83.68
Ladakh	2	1	50.00
Madhya Pradesh	241	131	54.36
Maharashtra	1208	869	71.94
Manipur	53	43	81.13
Meghalaya	30	23	76.67
Mizoram	24	17	70.83
Nagaland	32	26	81.25
Odisha	103	31	30.10
Puducherry	22	13	59.09
Punjab	177	125	70.62
Rajasthan	166	46	27.71
Sikkim	4	2	50.00
Tamil Nadu	431	339	78.65
Telangana	150	107	71.33
Tripura	20	11	55.00
Uttar Pradesh	259	108	41.70
Uttarakhand	33	13	39.39
West Bengal	385	329	85.45
Daman and Diu (No Member)	0	0	0.00
	6176	3999	64.75

1. Registered and Beneficiary Colleges:

Fig. 1

From the above chart it is clear that few registered colleges have not renewed themselves. The Maharashtra state have

maximum registered colleges and also active colleges.

2. Total number of Registered Member colleges of NLIST in India:

Fig. 2

In India the colleges registered themselves for NLIST e- resources are 3999. Out of which Maharashtra state achieved 19.6%,

the highest number of total registered colleges.

3. Total number of Active Member colleges of NLIST in India:

Fig. 3

The chart shows that colleges from Daman & Diu and Chandigarh state have not renewed NLIST membership for year 2022-23 yet.

4. Ratio of Active Users to Beneficiary Colleges:

As per the data available on NLIST website (<https://nlist.inflibnet.ac.in/>) as on 20/09/2022 11:45 am. the total number of active users are 616358 and the number of beneficiary colleges are 3999. So, the ratio of active users to beneficiary colleges can be calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Ratio of active users to beneficiary colleges} &= \frac{\text{Total Number of Active Users}}{\text{Total Number of Member Colleges}} \\ &= \frac{616358}{3999} \\ &= 154.12 \end{aligned}$$

In average there are 154.12 active users in each institute. But as compared to the total number of the students studying in the institutes the number of active users is very less.

In NLIST the majority of materials are related to reference books and journals and those materials are research oriented. The data shows that the major number of students are not interested in using NLIST e-resources.

5. Top 10 College Users (Based on August 2022 Usage):

1	CSSR & SRRM Degree & P G College, Kadapa, Andhra Pradesh
2	Selvam Arts & Science College (Autonomous), Namakkal, Tamil Nadu
3	Sri Indu College of Engineering & Technology, Hyderabad, Telangana
4	Bharathiyar Arts and Science College for Women, Attur Tk, Salem Dt., Tamil Nadu
5	St. Claret College, Bangalore, Bangalore, Karnataka
6	Vellalar College For Women (Autonomous), Erode, Tamil Nadu
7	Auxilium College, Vellore, Tamil Nadu
8	Sri Sarada College for Women, Salem, Tamil Nadu
9	JSSPS Arts, Com & Sci College Goveli, Kalyan, Maharashtra
10	Mahatma Gandhi Govt. P. G. College Kharsia, Kharsia, Chhattisgarh

The above table shows that the users from CSSR & SRRM Degree & P G College, Kadapa, Andhra Pradesh are Highest in number and the users from colleges in Tamil Nadu state are most active in August 2022 as 5 colleges of the state are in Top 10 list. The states like Telangana, Karnataka, Maharashtra and

Chhattisgarh are also doing great work by using NLIST. Maharashtra state has maximum number of Registrations and Beneficiaries but the top college from Maharashtra comes 9th in the Top 10 list. Other states also need to improve their usage of e-resources provided by NLIST.

6. Top 10 Beneficiary States:

Sr. No.	Name of State	Registered Colleges	Active Colleges	Percentage of Beneficiaries
1	Maharashtra	1208	869	71.94
2	Karnataka	734	486	66.21
3	Tamil Nadu	431	339	78.65
4	West Bengal	385	329	85.45
5	Kerala	288	241	83.68
6	Assam	248	195	78.63
7	Andhra Pradesh	258	175	67.83
8	Chhattisgarh	188	138	73.40
9	Madhya Pradesh	241	131	54.36
10	Punjab	177	125	70.62
36	Daman and Diu	0	0	0.00
	Total	6176	3999	64.75

Total 6176 colleges are registered for NLIST out of which 3999(64.75%) colleges have renewed the membership by paying fee. The inactive colleges are 2177 (35.25%).The table indicates that Maharashtra state has maximum number of registered colleges as well as maximum number of active colleges. The state of Daman and Diu,no college is registered for NLIST.

7. Present status of colleges registered in India:

There are 42343 colleges in India but only 6176 colleges have registered for NLIST programme and out of those 3999 colleges has renewed for 2022-23

Findings and Suggestions:

In the present study the author focuses on the NLIST registered member colleges in India. The major findings of the study and the suggestions have been summarized below:

Findings:

- Total 6176 colleges in India are registered themselves for NLIST consortium.
- Total 3999 colleges became active by renewing membership after paying renewal fee.
- 64.75 % registered colleges are active.
- The Maharashtra have maximum registered and active colleges. Maharashtra have 19.6% of total registered colleges.
- Chandigarh have one college registered but not renewed NLIST membership for year 2022-23. There is no college in Daman & Diu state registered with NLIST.
- Total active users of all active colleges are 616358. The ratio of active users to beneficiary colleges is 154.12
- The states like Tamil Nadu, Telangana, Karnataka, Maharashtra and Chhattisgarh are doing great work. Tamil Nadu has 5 colleges in Top 10 list of active colleges.

- The percentage of active colleges differs from the percentage of registered colleges.

Suggestions:

- All the registered colleges should renew the membership of NLIST by paying required fee.
- Every college in India should register themselves to NLIST programme so that each and every student, researcher and teacher can get access to e-resources available through this consortium.
- College administrator of member colleges should activate the users promptly.
- Users from all states should use e-resources because it is a rich source of current information.
- Every college administrator must apply for the membership of NLIST and renew every year to help students, teachers and researchers.
- INFLIBNET center should encourage the higher education institutes to register them in NLIST programme and help students, research and faculty members to connect with the E-resources available through NLIST.
- The number and frequency of awareness programs and training programs should be increased.

Conclusion:

The project NLIST is one of the best source of E-Resources available for colleges in India. But the registration and renewal of it by colleges is found very low in number. To connecting users to e-resources should be put at first priority. Both colleges and INFLIBNET should act vigorously to increase membership and also renew membership every year. It will help students, research and faculty

members to improve the quality of education, research and overall growth of nation.

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